

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Salem Hussein****FIRST NAME: Ahmed Yahya****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

IMPORTANCE OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

When most people think of academic writing, they think of thesis papers composed by graduate students and research articles written by professional scholars while these are two great examples of academic writing, the concept can apply more generally to include much wide variety of tasks and objectives. Academic writing is a variety of academic English convey research in writing that means there are many different kinds of academic writing from literature reviews to research papers to abstracts and reports. While trying to compare and contrast all the many different types of academic writing is a tall order, the most important thing to remember is that generally each kind of academic writing has its own rules and conventions as such it's important to the rules and expectations for a particular style of academic writing before starting to write.

2) GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

There are focused and specific expectations when producing a piece of academic writing, academic writing is used to answer the research questions, these questions are either provided by a course instructor or developed by the writer or researcher. Good academic writing starts with focus and specific questions to be answered. Writing down

everything you know about a topic is not enough to make a good academic essay. Analyzing, then answering the essay's question or task is central. Be sure that you understand exactly what the question requires you to do. Identify the key words (like discuss or analyze) and clarify the approach you are required to take (**EUCLID 2015, 2-5**).

a) Academic writing emphasizes logical reasoning over emotional or sensory perceptions

Facts are important than feelings, writing clearly means thinking clearly, and so effective academic writing demonstrates clear critical thinking and ability to make argument stronger by supporting them with evidence. After you have researched and your ideas are more developed, write a second essay plan. It will help you work out how to answer the question and how the essay will be structured. After you do some research and note making, draw up a second plan:

- Decide on a possible answer to the question (in terms of the research you have done),
- Decide on the information you will use to answer the question,
- Look through your notes and choose examples to provide evidence to support your answer,
- Decide which points you will discuss, and in which order, and
- Write all this down in point form and this will be your essay plan (**EUCLID 2015, 3**).

b) Academic writing must be clear

Academic writing must be clear, English is both a low context and reader responsible language, by this I mean readers will depend on what's been written and believe its writers job to make his or her argument as comprehensive as possible. Paraphrases are the ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in **your** own words. In a paper it does not look very good if you have too many quotes. So you will need to paraphrase at times. (**EUCLID 2015, 23-28**).

c) Academic writing must be coherent

This means there are logical connections between sentences, one way to do this is to begin sentences with information that relates back to the previous sentence, it also means that paragraphs are unified around the single idea and all that information are included in a piece of writing helps to create an effective argument used to answer the research questions. Most essays are dramatically improved by careful editing. If possible,

put your essay aside for a few days before you begin to edit. This gives you time to think further about your answer and arguments and return to your work with a fresh perspective. Don't panic if/ when you find faults in your essay - this is part of the process. If you find that you need more information, or your argument has holes in it, keep calm and concentrate on fixing the problem. Once you have a well-organized and fairly complete draft:

- Check the overall structure of your essay; does it have a clear introduction, body and conclusion?

- Make sure that each paragraph has a clear main point that relates to the argument. Make sure that the paragraphs are arranged in logical sequence.

- Revise sentences. Make sure the words you use mean what you think they mean. Check punctuation and spelling. A good dictionary is a useful tool.

- Check transition signals. Be sure that a reader can follow the sequence of ideas from sentence to sentence, and from paragraph to paragraph.

Questions to ask yourself

- Have I answered the question as directly and comprehensively as possible?

- Does the argument make sense? Is it balanced and well researched?

- Is the evidence relevant to and supportive of my argument?

- Have I used a consistent citation style? Have I referenced all my quotes and paraphrases?

- If there were any special instructions or guidelines for this assignment, have I followed them?

- Have I remained within the set word limit? (EUCLID 2015, 42-46).

d) Steps in the writing process

First, "Analyze the task": This involves clarifying your purpose for writing and identifying your target audience, an academic essay should answer a question or task (Euclid 2015, 2).

Second, "Planning your argument": you need to develop a main claim and decide how you will support this claim using evidence; an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence (EUCLID 2015, 2).

Third, "Research": this is necessary in order to gather quality fact-based objective evidence that you need to create the argument you will use to support your main claim. A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers. Therefore, reading and researching are vital to essay writing. Researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question (**EUCLID 2015, 3**).

Forth, "Start writing and engage in the drafting process": no good writing is done overnight, it's important to produce multiple drafts and to both edit and proofread your writing, while it's important to consider things like punctuation and proper spelling, it's even more important to how well you've structured your argument and the information in your writing. Write a first draft to try out the structure and framework of your essay. A draft essay will help you work out how you will answer the question and which evidence and examples you will use; and how your argument will be structured. Once you have a draft, you can work on writing well. Your first draft will not be your final essay; think of it as raw material you will refine through editing and redrafting (**EUCLID 2015, 4**). To do this it's a good idea to ask for comments from peers and colleagues. Block quotations are not only introduced with punctuation appropriate to the syntax but also followed by commentary.

3) CONCLUSION

Finally, there are many benefits of investing your time and energy in becoming proficient academic writer. Academic writing is an important skill to master for a wide variety of professional and personal reasons. First, it allows writers to make individual contributions to the ongoing dialogues in their fields; it allows individuals a greater voice and ability to participate in conversations about topics important to them additionally by mastering the skills necessary to become an effective academic writer a person also becomes an effective researcher and critical thinker. Academic writing is a marketable skill that improves one's professional qualifications and makes one a more attractive candidate for potential employers. So, in the end we see that academic writing is about much more than just the act of writing which is itself not simply a skill but a collection of skills in addition to putting your thoughts on the page, effective academic writing involves critical thinking, the ability to create a convincing argument, and a good research skill.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed December 11, 2019).

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